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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF SUSTAINED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS OF CAPTOPRIL

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation concerns the development of Sustained release matrix tablets of Captopril, which after oral administration are designed to prolong the duration up to 12 hrs and thereby increase patient compliance, reduced frequency of administration and increase therapeutic efficacy. Ten batches of tablets were fabricated containing Captopril, polymers HPMC K100M, ethyl cellulose, sodium CMC and other excipients. All the batches were formulated by direct compression. The evaluation was done on the granules which include compressibility, flow property. The tablets were evaluated for appearance, thickness, hardness, assay, weight variation, friability, and in vitro release studies. The results obtained were satisfactory and complies with the Pharmacopoeial specifications. The formulation containing HPMC K100M and ethyl cellulose (F₇) showed slower release as compare to other formulations. The in-vitro release data was treated with mathematical equations. Thus the combination of HPMC K100M and ethyl cellulose (1:1) shows satisfactory retarding release of Captopril from matrix to 12 hrs.

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Introduction: Sustained release technology is relatively new field and as a consequence, research in the field has been extremely fertile and has produced many discoveries. With many drugs, the basic goal is to achieve a steady state blood level that is therapeutically effective and non-toxic for an extended period of time. The design of proper dosage form is an important element to accomplish this goal. Sustained release, sustained action, prolonged action, controlled release, extended action, timed release and depot dosage form are term used to identify drug delivery system that are designed to achieve prolonged therapeutic effect by continuously releasing medication over an extended period of time after administration of a single dose. In the case of oral sustained released dosage form, an effect is for several hours depending upon residence time of formulation in the GIT. The success of a therapy depends on selection of the appropriate delivery system as much as drug itself.¹ Sustained release dosage forms are designed to complement pharmaceutical activity of the medication in order to achieve better selectivity and longer duration of action. Captopril belongs to class Angiotensin Converting Enzyme inhibitor (ACE inhibitor). It effects the rennin-Angiotensin system and inhibits the conversion of relatively inactive Angiotensin I to active Angiotensin II. Thus, ACE inhibitors attenuate or abolish responses to Angiotensin I but not to Angiotensin II. Hence the inhibition of ACE therefore may induce the effect unrelated to reducing the level of Angiotensin II. ACE inhibition increase bradykinin synthesis which stimulate prostaglandin biosynthesis. Bradykinin and prostaglandin contribute pharmacological effect of ACE inhibitor. All these effects produce pharmacological actions like vasodilatation etc which ultimately decrease the blood pressure. Captopril is freely water-soluble and has a half-life 1.9 hours. It is usually prescribed to patients who are chronically ill and require long term use for therapeutic benefits. Development of a captopril oral formulation would be a significant

advantage for patient compliance accompanied by minimization of the drug side effects as a result of reduction in the drug blood concentration fluctuations, especially in long-term therapy.

Materials and Methods:

Materials: Ethylcellulose was purchased from SD Fine Chemicals Ltd (Mumbai India). HPMC K100M was gifted by Colorcon, India. Sodium CMC was gifted by Qualigens Fine Chemicals, Mumbai. Captopril was a gift from Modi-Mundipharma Private Ltd(U.P,India). All the other chemicals used were of high analytical grade.

Method: Captopril SR Tablets were prepared by direct compression technique.

Sifting: Drug was passed through 40# sieve. Sodium CMC, Lactose, Ethyl Cellulose & HPMC K100M was passed through 30# sieve. Talc and Magnesium stearate were passed though 40 # sieve.

Mixing & Lubrication: Captopril, Lactose, Sodium CMC, Ethyl Cellulose & HPMC K100M was mixed in double cone blender for 10min. at 18 RPM. Add Magnesium stearate and Talc into above mixture and mixed it for 3min. at 18 RPM.

Compression: The prepared blend was compressed. The compatibility of the drug and formulation is an important study; compatibility evaluation was carried out using infra-red spectra. Infrared spectrum of formulated granules and drug alone were recorded and observed between 400 nm and 4000 nm. Infra - red spectrum of pure drug was also run individually.

Evaluation of Granules

Angle of Repose

The angle of repose of granules was determined by the funnel method. The accurately weighed granules were taken in a funnel. The height of the funnel was adjusted in such a way that the tip of the funnel just touched the apex of the heap of the granules. The granules were allowed to flow through the funnel freely onto the surface. The diameter of the powder cone was measured and angle of repose was calculated using the

following equation²: $\tan \theta = h/r$

where h and r are the height and radius of the powder cone.

Bulk Density

Both loose bulk density (LBD) and tapped bulk density (TBD) were determined. A quantity of 2 g of powder from each formula, previously lightly shaken to break any agglomerates formed, was introduced into a 10ml measuring cylinder. After the initial volume was observed, the cylinder was allowed to fall under its own weight onto a hard surface from the height of 2.5 cm at 2 second intervals. The tapping was continued until no further change in volume was noted. LBD and TBD were calculated using the following formula³:

LBD = weight of the powder/volume of the packing
 TBD = weight of the powder/tapped volume of the packing

Compressibility Index

The compressibility index of the granules was determined by carr's compressibility index⁴:
 Carr's index (%) = [(TBD - LBD) × 100]/TBD

Drug Content

An accurately weighed amount of powdered Captopril granules (100 mg) was extracted with

water and the solution was filtered through 0.45µ membrane (nunc, new delhi, india). The absorbance was measured at 203 nm after suitable dilution.

Evaluation of Tablets

Thickness

The thickness of the tablets was determined using a thickness gauge (mitutoyo, new delhi, india). Five tablets from each batch were used, and average values were calculated.

Weight Variation Test

To study weight variation, 20 tablets of each formulation were weighed using an electronic balance (denver APX-100, arvada, colorado), and the test was performed according to the official method.⁶

Hardness and Friability

For each formulation, the hardness and friability of 6 tablets were determined using the Monsanto hardness tester (cadmach, ahmedabad, india) and the roche friabilator (campbell electronics, mumbai, india), respectively.

Formulation of captopril matrix tablets

Each quantity mentioned will be taken in mgs
 Total weight of the tablet = 200mg
 Each tablet contains = 25mg of the captopril

Table no: 1 - Formula

Sr .no	Ingredient	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
1	Captopril	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
2	HPMC K-100	30	60	-	-	-	-	30	-	30	20
3	Ethyl cellulose	-	-	30	60	-	-	30	30	-	20
4	Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose	-	-	-	-	30	60	-	30	30	20
5	Lactose	129	99	129	99	129	99	99	99	99	99
6	Magnesium Stearate	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
7	Talc	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

Uniformity of content:

Five randomly selected tablets were weighed and powdered. The powdered tablet equivalent to 20 mg drug in one tablet was taken and transferred in a 250ml flask containing 100ml of 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2) and phosphate buffer pH 6.8. The flask was on a shaken on a flask shaker for 24 hours and was kept for 12 hours for the sedimentation of undissolved materials. The solution is filtered through Whatmann filter paper(0.45 μ m). 10ml of this filtrate was taken and appropriate dilution was made. The samples were analyzed at 203nm using UV visible spectrophotometer. The drug content was determined from the standard curve prepared at λ max 203 nm.

In vitro dissolution studies:

In vitro dissolution study was carried out using USP I apparatus (basket apparatus) in 900 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 for 12 hours. The temperature of the dissolution medium was kept at 37 \pm 0.5 $^{\circ}$ C and the basket was set at 50 rpm. 1 ml of sample solution was withdrawn at specified interval of time. The absorbance of the withdrawn samples was measured at λ max 203 nm using UV visible spectrophotometer. The concentration was determined from the standard curve of captopril prepared in distilled water at λ max 203 nm. Cumulative percentage of drug release was calculated using the equation obtained from a standard curve

Swelling index

Swelling of tablet involves the absorption of a liquid resulting in an increase in weight and volume. Liquid uptake by the particle may be due to saturation of capillary spaces within the particles or hydration of macromolecule. The liquid enters the particles or hydration of macromolecules. The liquid enters the particles through pores and bind to large molecule; breaking the hydrogen bond and resulting in the swelling of particle. The extent of swelling can be measured in terms of %weight gain by the tablet.

The swelling index of tablets was determined in 0.1

N HCl (pH 1.2) at room temperature. After each interval the tablet was removed from beaker, remove the excess buffer by using filter paper and weighed again upto 7 hrs. The swelling index was calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{Swelling index (SI)} = \frac{(W_t - W_0)}{W_0} \times 100$$

Where, W_t = Weight of tablet at time t.

W_0 = Initial weight of tablet

Modelling of dissolution profiles

In vitro dissolution has been recognized as an important element in drug development under certain assessment of Bioequivalence. Several theories/kinetics models describe drug dissolution from immediate and modified release dosage forms. There are several models to represent the drug dissolution profiles where f_t is a function of 't' (time) related to the amount of drug dissolved from the pharmaceutical dosage system. Whenever a new solid dosage form is developed or produced, the drug release/dissolution from solid pharmaceutical dosage form is necessary to ensure that the drug dissolution occurs in an appropriate manner. Several theories/ kinetic models describe drug dissolution form immediate and modified release dosage. These represents the drug dissolution profiles where f_t is a function of 't' (time) related to the amount of drug dissolved from the pharmaceutical dosage forms. The quantitative interpretation of the value obtained from the dissolution assay is facilitated by mathematical equation which translates the dissolution curve in function of some parameters related with the pharmaceutical dosage forms.

In the present study, data of the in vitro release were fitted to different equations and kinetic models to explain the release kinetics of captopril from the matrix tablets. The kinetic models used were a Zero order equation, First order, Higuchi release and Korsmeyer-Peppas models.

Mathematical models^{7,8&9}

Zero Order Kinetics:

Drug dissolution from pharmaceutical dosage forms

that do not disaggregate and release the drug slowly (assuming that area does not change and no equilibrium conditions are obtained) can be represented by the following equation;

$$Q_t = Q_0 + k_0 t$$

Where, Q_t = amount of drug released in time 't',

Q_0 = initial amount of drug in the solution,

k_0 = zero order release constant.

The pharmaceutical dosage forms following this profile, release the same amount of drug by unit of time and it is the ideal method of drug release in order to achieve a pharmacological prolonged action. This relation can be used to describe the drug dissolution of several types of modified release pharmaceutical dosage form, as in the case of some transdermal system, as well as matrix tablets with low soluble drugs, coated form, osmotic systems, etc.

First Order Kinetics

The application of this model to drug dissolution studies was first proposed by Gibaldi and Feldman.

The following relation can express this model:

$$\text{Log } Q_t = \text{Log } Q_0 + k_1 t / 2.303$$

Where, Q_t = amount of drug released in time 't',

Q_0 = initial amount of drug in the solution,

k_1 = first order release constant.

The pharmaceutical dosage forms following this dissolution profile, such as those containing water soluble drugs in porous matrices, release the drug in a way that is proportional to the amount of drug remaining in its interior, in such way, that the amount of drug released by unit of time diminish.

Higuchi Model

Higuchi developed several theoretical models to study the release of water soluble drugs incorporated in semisolid and/or solid matrixes. Simplified Higuchi model can be expressed by following equation:

$$f_t = k_H t^{1/2}$$

Where, k_H = Higuchi diffusion constant, f_t = fraction of drug dissolved in time 't'.

Higuchi describes drug release as a diffusion process based in the Fick's law, square root time

dependent. This relation can be used to describe the drug dissolution from several types modified release pharmaceutical dosage forms, as in the case of some transdermal systems and matrix tablets with water soluble drugs.

Korsmeyer-Peppas Model

Korsmeyer et al. developed a simple, semi empirical model, relating exponentially the drug release to the elapsed time (t);

$$f_t = at^n$$

Where, a = constant incorporating structural and geometric characteristics of the drug dosage form,

n = release exponent,

$f_t = M_t/M_\infty$ = fraction release of drug.

Comparison of dissolution profiles: The dissolutions profiles of products with theoretical dissolution profile were compared using a similarity factor (f_2). The dissolution profiles are considered to be similar when (f_2) is between 0-100, the method was first reported by Moore and Flanner. The dissolutions profiles of products were compared using a similarity factor (f_2). This similarity factor is a logarithmic reciprocal square root transformation of one plus the average mean squared (the average sum of squares) differences of drug % dissolution between the test and reference products over all time point

$$F_2 = 50 \times \text{Log} \left\{ \left[1 + \frac{1}{n} \sum (R-T)^2 \right]^{-0.5} \times 100 \right\}$$

Where n is the number of dissolution time point and R and T are the references and test dissolution values at time t. Two dissolution profiles are considered similar when the (f_2) value is 0 to 100.

Stability studies:

The success of an effective formulation was evaluated only through the stability studies. The purpose of stability testing was to obtain a stable product which assures its safety and efficacy up to the end of shelf life at defined storage condition and peak profile.

The prepared matrix tablet (F_7) of captopril were placed on plastic tubes containing desiccant and stored at ambient conditions like room temp. (RT) and 40°C & 75% RH for a period of 30 days.

**Results and discussion:
Compatibility studies**

Figure. No 1: IR Spectrum of Pure Drug(Captopril)

Figure. No 2: IR Spectrum of HPMC K 100

Figure. No 3: IR Spectrum of Ethyl cellulose

Figure. No 4: IR Spectrum of Sodium CMC

Figure. No 5 IR Spectrum of Captopril+ HPMC K100+Ethyl cellulose+Sodium CMC

Evaluation of powders

Table no 2: Preformulation Studies of Powders:

Parameter	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
Bulk density	0.312	0.303	0.294	0.322	0.333	0.303	0.38	0.40	0.322	0.333
Tapped density	0.357	0.358	0.344	0.370	0.384	0.370	0.47	0.55	0.384	0.40
Carr's index (%)	12.60	15.3	14.53	12.97	13.28	18.10	19.1	27.2	16.14	16.75
Hausner ratio	1.14	1.18	1.17	1.14	1.15	1.22	1.23	1.37	1.17	1.20
Angle of repose(θ)	39 $^{\circ}$ 6'	38 $^{\circ}$ 6'	40 $^{\circ}$	37 $^{\circ}$ 5'	39 $^{\circ}$ 7'	31 $^{\circ}$	27 $^{\circ}$	39 $^{\circ}$ 8'	30 $^{\circ}$	35 $^{\circ}$

Physico – chemical evaluation of matrix tablets:

The results of the thickness, Hardness, weight variation, drug content, friability, disintegration time of tablet are shown in Table (3).

Table no 3. Results of Thickness, weight variation, Hardness and Friability

Parameter Batch	Weight Variation (mg)	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Thickness (mm)
F 1	Pass	6.7	0.74	3.08
F 2	Pass	6.4	0.34	3.09
F 3	Pass	6.9	0.48	3.10
F 4	Pass	6.6	0.59	3.11
F 5	Pass	6.9	0.54	3.09
F 6	Pass	6.3	0.50	3.10
F 7	Pass	7.2	0.69	3.08
F 8	Pass	7.1	0.49	3.07
F 9	Pass	6.8	0.44	3.10
F 10	Pass	7.4	0.39	3.07

Drug content uniformity

The results of drug content of tablets are shown in Table (4). The drug content of tablets was found to vary between 95.40% to 98.1%.

Table no 4: Result of Drug content uniformity

Parameter Batch	Drug Content (%)
F 1	97.22
F 2	95.40
F 3	97.08
F 4	96.3
F 5	95.55
F 6	98.1
F 7	96.6
F 8	98.2
F 9	97.5
F 10	96.8

In vitro Release Study

As follows the dissolution profiles shows the comparative release profile of Captopril with different concentration of different polymer from batches F1, F2, F3, F4, F5, F6, F7, F8, F9 & F10 of matrix tablet.

Figure No 6: cumulative percentage drug release of captopril matrix tablets.

Table no 5: Result of In vitro Release Studies

S.no.	Time	F-1	F-2	F-3	F-4	F-5	F-6	F-7	F-8	F-9	F-10
1	1	18.4	16.3	20.1	31.9	15.8	14.3	16.01	19.3	18.7	10.28
2	2	31.62	27.61	33.2	45.3	26.31	24.11	23.56	21.62	23.42	11.89
3	3	48.62	44.51	49.2	57.9	39.19	36.01	32.73	35.62	32.42	23.23
4	4	56.13	56.12	58.3	63.24	46.9	42.42	43.26	42.33	38.75	36.38
5	5	64.76	62.16	64.6	71.66	54.44	50.64	54.66	53.14	44.14	51.02
6	6	76.70	74.99	77.9	80.99	65.87	62.87	63.29	57.89	50.54	58.27
7	7	88.55	80.75	82.4	85.33	71.62	68.31	71.77	62.33	58.89	63.72
8	8	91.51	83.20	85.0	89.67	82.17	77.16	79.23	69.87	66.13	71.48
9	9	94.98	89.01	88.5	92.02	87.63	85.72	85.43	74.63	71.48	76.94
10	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	91.12	78.28	77.82	82.51
11	11	-	-	-	-	-	-	94.38	84.65	86.49	88.09
12	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	96.65	88.11	92.06	94.87

Figure. No. 7

Invitro cumulative % drug release v/s time for formulation (F1 TO F10) of captopril matrix tablets [zero order rate]

Figure No. 8

Log cumulative % drug retained v/s time for formulation (F1 to F10) of captopril matrix tablets [first order rate kinetics]

Figure No. 9

Cumulative % drug released v/s root time for formulation (F1 to F10) of captopril matrix tablets [Higuchi classical diffusion equation]

Figure No. 10: Log cumulative % drug released v/s log time for formulation (F1 to F10) of captopril matrix tablets [Peppas exponential equation]

Figure No 11: Cube root of % drug retained v/s time for formulation (F1 to F10) of captopril matrix tablets [hixson-crowell]

Table no:7

Kinetic values obtained from in- vitro release data of F1-F10.

Code	Zero-order R ²	Zero-order slope	First order R ²	First order slope	Higuchi R ²	Higuchi slope	Peppas R ²	Peppas Slope	Hixson Crowell R ²	Hixson Crowell Slope
F1	0.939	12.08	0.953	-0.142	0.966	34.33	0.680	1.397	0.987	-0.33
F2	0.931	11.30	0.987	-0.106	0.965	32.27	0.698	1.402	0.994	-0.271
F3	0.882	11.62	0.992	-0.106	0.978	31.9	0.647	1.344	0.991	-0.269
F4	0.736	12.40	0.992	-0.118	0.995	31.84	0.547	1.239	0.987	-0.281
F5	0.972	10.48	0.958	-0.095	0.956	30.36	0.704	1.378	0.987	-0.250
F6	0.983	9.95	0.952	-0.086	0.945	29.23	0.722	1.384	0.983	-0.233
F7	0.951	9.92	0.942	-0.118	0.963	31.43	0.740	1.249	0.989	-0.264
F8	0.914	8.29	0.980	-0.072	0.979	26.99	0.691	1.161	0.994	-0.188
F9	0.958	8.01	0.909	-0.079	0.943	26.70	0.697	1.155	0.964	-0.198
F10	0.977	8.45	0.922	-0.095	0.934	30.79	0.836	1.372	0.979	-0.220

Table no 8**Swelling Index of Tablets of Batch F1 toF10**

Code	TIME (HRS)							
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
F1	0	57.5	67.4	75.5	92.2	104.5	111.3	119.2
F2	0	63.5	74.5	86.1	98.2	107.5	118.2	124.5
F3	0	34.65	45.54	56.1	64.3	72.3	85.5	96.2
F4	0	42.01	50.5	62.5	68.0	74.5	91.59	99.01
F5	0	49.0	53.50	65.5	79.0	90.50	103.5	107.5
F6	0	51.0	61.5	74.1	84.5	92.5	110.1	115.5
F7	0	69.0	76.50	94.50	102.0	114.0	125.5	131.7
F8	0	52.2	65.1	80.5	92.5	101.2	118.5	125.5
F9	0	66.5	74.1	88.2	98.5	103.2	114.3	127.0
F10	0	57.1	70.1	82.5	90.5	99.5	106.1	112.5

Discussion:

In batch F1, 30gm of HPMC K100M was used as a sustained release polymer. Preformulation study and physico chemical evaluation of matrix tablet was conducted and results are shown in table 2 and 3. In vitro dissolution study result of F1 showed 94.98% drug release within 9 hours. Thus 12 hour sustained release profile was not achieved. So in next batch F2 it was decided to double the amount of HPMC K100M. In batch F2, 60 gm of HPMC K100M was used as compared to 30 gm used in batch F1. Results obtained of dissolution study conducted showed 89.01% cumulative drug release within 9 hours. The batch F2 fails to sustain drug release up to 12 hrs hence next batch was formulated. In batch F3, 30 gm of ethyl cellulose was used in place of HPMC K100M. Blend was compressed and in vitro dissolution study was conducted. The results showed 88.5% drug release within 9 hours which again failed to desired drug release profile. In batch F4, 60 gm of ethyl cellulose and lactose as diluents was used.

Results of in vitro dissolution study showed 92.02% cumulative drug release in 10 hrs. Batch F5 was formulated using 30 gm sodium CMC in place of ethyl cellulose. Results of in vitro dissolution study showed 87.63% cumulative drug release within 9 hours. In F6 amount of sodium CMC was increased to 60 gm from initially used 30 gm in batch F5. Dissolution study showed 85.72% drug release in 9 hours. Thus now it was decided to use combination of different polymers used in initial batches for next batch. In batch F7, 30 gm of HPMC K100M and 30 gm of ethyl cellulose was used in combination for preparation sustained release tablets of Captopril. Results obtained of in vitro dissolution study showed 12 hour sustained drug release which is in compliance with desired drug release profile. Cumulative drug release of batch F7 was 96.65%. The batch F8 was formulated by using combination of ethyl cellulose and sodium CMC. Results showed 88.11% cumulative drug release within the span of 12 hours. In batch F9, HPMC

Table No-9 Stability studies of formulation F7 at room temperature.

Time (hr)	Cumulative % Drug Release	
	Initial	After 30Days
0	0	0
1	21.3	18.95
2	31.52	26.49
3	42.52	35.98
4	55.53	45.62
5	68.05	56.53
6	73.29	63.52
7	77.95	72.76
8	85.81	78.01
9	88.55	88.64
10	90.01	91.61
11	94.38	93.84
12	96.65	95.45
Hardness	7.2	7.0
Friability	0.69	0.71
Drug content	96.6	95.00

Table No-10 Stability studies of formulation F7 at 40°C.

Time (hr)	Cumulative % Drug Release	
	Initial	After 30Days
0	0	0
1	21.3	19.29
2	31.52	27.41
3	42.52	36.54
4	55.53	46.53
5	68.05	57.32
6	73.29	65.22
7	77.95	73.01
8	85.81	77.99
9	88.55	88.70
10	90.01	91.11
11	94.38	93.54
12	96.65	96.45
Hardness	7.2	6.9
Friability	0.69	0.74
Drug content	96.6	95.92

Summary:

Oral route of drug administration is oldest and safest mode of drug administration. It possesses several advantages. It provides accurate dosing without assistance of administration. In conventional oral drug delivery system, there is little or no control over release of drug, and effective concentration at the target site can be achieved by administration of grossly excessive dosage form. Sustained release technology is relatively new field and as a consequence, research in the field has been extremely

fertile and has produced many discoveries. With many drugs, the basic goal is to achieve a steady state blood level that is therapeutically effective and non-toxic for an extended period of time. The design of proper dosage form is an important element to accomplish this goal. The present study was undertaken with an aim to formulate develop and evaluate Captopril sustained release tablets using different polymers by direct compression method. The successful application of the direct compression method in preparing the matrix type of sustained release dosage form depends on the selection of suitable matrix material. Captopril is an orally inhibitor of an

Angiotensin-converting enzyme, demonstrates excellent clinical effectiveness in the treatment of essential hypertension. However, the efficacy of captopril as a first choice of drug with antihypertensive action after oral dosing is limited to only 6-8 hrs. Therefore, clinical use requires captopril to be taken 3 times daily. Preformulation study was carried out results directed for the further course of formulation. Based on Preformulation studies different batches of Captopril were prepared using selected excipients. Granules were evaluated for bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, Hausner ratio. IR spectra studies revealed that the drug and polymers used were compatible. Various formulations of sustained release tablets of Captopril were developed using various polymers viz, hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, Ethyl cellulose, and Sodium CMC in different proportions and combinations by direct compression technique. The tablets were evaluated for physical characterization, in vitro release study and stability studies. The physical characteristics of the granules have complied with officials as per specification of Indian pharmacopeia. Results of in vitro release profile indicated that

formulation (F7) was the most promising formulation as the extent of drug release from this formulation was high as compared to other formulations.

Stability study was conducted on tablets of Batch F7 stored at room temperature, 40°C, and 2-8°C for one month. Tablets were evaluated for hardness, friability, in-vitro release profile and drug content. After one month no significant changes were observed in any of the studied parameters during the study period, thus it could be concluded that formulation was stable. It was concluded that the tablets of batch F7 had considerable swelling behaviors and in vitro drug release.

Conclusion:

From the above results it is concluded that formulation of sustained release tablet of Captopril containing HPMC K100M and ethyl cellulose (1:1) batch F7 can be taken as an optimized formulation of sustained release tablets.

From the present research it can be concluded that a successful sustain release tablet of Captopril can be formulated using HPMC K100M and ethyl cellulose

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